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**THE IMPORTANCE OF MORPHO-PHYSIOLOGICAL TRAITS IN WHEAT
SAMPLES RESISTANT TO YELLOW RUST UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE
CONDITIONS**

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Abstract: *A further increase in cultivation is mainly due to increased productivity and reduced losses due to various stress factors. Stress resistance is associated with the modification of the genetic system of plant cells and, as a result, changes in the course of some physiological and biochemical processes. In this regard, the collection of wheat germplasm, the analysis of their morphological, genetic and physiological characteristics are of great scientific and practical significance.*

Key words: *Photosynthesis, leaf area, wheat, carotenoid, grain yield.*

INTRODUCTION. Agriculture is one of the main sectors of economic development; constant provision of food security to the population is one of the important tasks of each country (Meliev *et al.*, 2023). Wheat is a primary crop for global food safety. Modern cultivars must combine high yield potential and grain quality with strong resistance to yellow rust and resilience to adverse environmental conditions (Awais *et al.*, 2025; Meliev *et al.*, 2021 Lachaud *et al.*, 2022). In the selection of high-yielding varieties, the interaction of genotype and environment is the main reason for differences in the yield of varieties in different conditions. Different genotypes respond differently to the same conditions, and at the same time, the same genotype responds differently to different environmental conditions (Torres *et al.*, 2013; Baboeva *et al.*, 2023). There is a decrease in wheat yield due to high temperatures, especially during grain filling, and the period of formation of crop components is shortens. Evaluation and identification of the wheat gene pool through the creation of natural and artificial high temperature stress environments is required. Also, high temperature can be useful in determining the main characteristics of wheat genotypes and selecting the desired genotypes (Khan *et al.*, 2022).

Proper phenotyping in breeding and its application in combination with molecular information in the genetic process will improve breeding efficiency (Bernardo, 2008). In this case, the process of indirect selection aimed at physiological traits is considered more effective than selection aimed at productive traits (Sabri *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, this study was undertaken to evaluate the differences in morphological and physiological traits for increasing the yield of heat-tolerant and temperature-sensitive genotypes. The purpose of the study is to identify key characteristics that may be useful in the selection and development of climate-resistant wheat.

Results. The influence of the external environment on productivity. Based on the results of the analysis of the yield of the samples, it was established that the average annual yield of the collection samples was $Y_i = 66.9$ c/ha, which is 3.9 c/ha higher than that of the standard variety Krasnodar - 99 (the annual average is 63.0 c/ha). In terms of yield, the standard variety showed high results in 17 samples. The overall average yield of all collection samples for three years was 66.9 c/ha, while for samples K-7 (70.7 c/ha), K-13 (71.6 c/ha), K-32 (67.7 c/ha), K-46 (68.9 c/ha), K-64 (77.6 c/ha) and K-89 (68.6 c/ha), the yield was above average.

When stress resistance was analyzed by productivity in our study, the Hydrothermal Coefficient

(HTC) in 2017 was 1.43, in the second year 2018-2.82 and in the third year 2019 - 0.69. The most favorable conditions during the study were observed in the first and third years. In the first year, the value of the environmental index was equal to $I_j=1.43$, and the total yield was 68.4 c/ha. In the second year, a relatively negative value was observed, equal to $I_j = - 2.8$. It was found that the total yield decreased to 64.8 c/ha. In the third year - relatively favorable conditions with $I_j = 0.69$, a total yield of 67.7 c/ha was obtained. These stressful metrological conditions make it possible to determine the adaptability of the studied samples.

In the second year of the study, the level of hydrothermal coefficient of atmospheric humidity decreased relatively, which led to a decrease in the total yield to 64.8 c/ha. It was found that in sample K-64 (78.5 c/ha), unlike samples with a high level in the first year, the yield did not decrease, which indicates a high genetic potential in terms of its own productivity.

Stable favorable conditions were observed during the third year of research and samples K-8 (76.3 c/ha), K-13 (74.7 c/ha), K-20 (74.3 c/ha), K-21 (69.3 c/ha), K-32 (72.0 c/ha), K-46 (69.7 c/ha), K-56 (72.0 c/ha), K-64 (78 .0 c/ha) and K-89 (71.3 c/ha) showed a positive result in the third year. Over the course of three years, it was noted that samples K-100, K-74 and K-64 were resistant to stress conditions and had low yield variability, and samples K-7, K-13, K-46 and K-89 had medium stability.

During three years of research, the environmental plasticity indicators (b_i) and stability coefficient (S_i^2) of the samples were studied. The yield of the samples showed different adaptive properties under the influence of the external environment. It was found that the variability of samples K-64 ($b_i = 0.5$, $S_i^2 = 1.8$), K-74 ($b_i = 0.7$, $S_i^2 = 1.9$) and K-100 ($b_i = 0.4$, $S_i^2 = 0.9$) was relatively low, indicating their resistance to stressful conditions. Samples K-8 ($b_i = 5.6$, $S_i^2 = 10.5$), K-13 ($b_i = 2.7$, $S_i^2 = 27.7$), K-20 ($b_i = 5.8$, $S_i^2 = 120.0$), K-21 ($b_i = 3.4$, $S_i^2 = 34.7$) and K-41 ($b_i = 4.0$, $S_i^2 = 10.1$) are rated with a very high level of environmental ductility and stability.

The relationship between quantitative indicators and physiological properties of selected samples; the correlation of the physiological properties of samples under conditions of high temperature and water deficiency stress, during the ripening of wheat grain, with quantitative traits that ensure yield is analyzed. In the analysis of the indicators of the leaf surface of the samples, the average annual indicator for the leaf surface of the collection samples was 63.6 ± 6.42 cm. The lowest indicator was observed in samples K-8 (50.1 ± 1.98), the highest - K-64 (73.0 ± 7.36). 9 samples showed results above average. 9 samples were identified that had a high rate compared to the average of all samples. Samples K-60, k-56 and k-89 differed in leaf length (29.2 ± 1.64 ; 28.1 ± 2.20 and 30.0 ± 0.80 cm), but were low in leaf width. In contrast, in sample K-21, the leaf length (28.3 ± 1.30) was relatively short, and the higher leaf width (2.48 ± 0.10) resulted in an increase in leaf surface (69.9 ± 2.35). In our studies, yields were also higher in samples with larger leaf areas. It was noted that the leaf surface of samples above 70 cm^2 changes the yield in the range of 65-77 c/ha, the weight of 1000 grains - in the range of 45-50 g. The presence of a correlation between the number of leaves and the yield indicator was noted in the results of statistical analysis. Based on its results, it was found that there is an average positive ($r = 0.58$) correlation between leaf surface and yield, and a weak positive ($r = 0.29$) correlation for the weight of 1000 grains.

The dependence of the chlorophyll content in the studied samples on the influence of the external environment has established that the overall average of three-year studies of the chlorophyll content in the samples is 2.63 ± 0.26 mg, and for the variety "Krasnodarskaya -99" (2.34 ± 0.12), that is, 0.29 mg more chlorophyll is synthesized. It was noted that in samples with a total chlorophyll content of more than 2.50 mg, the leaf surface was above 60 cm^2 , and the yield was above 60 c/ha in 85% of the samples. In samples K-7, K-46, K-13 and K-64, the highest result among the samples was observed in terms of the amount of chlorophyll, productivity and leaf area, as well as the daily net productivity of photosynthesis. The low amount of chlorophylls in samples K-41, K-47 and K-61 led to low daily photosynthesis, which led to a decrease in productivity. It was found that the yield of these samples is affected by low chlorophyll content. Since in samples K-7, K-13, K-32, K-46, K-64 and K-89 with a high content of chlorophyll "a", the yield was higher than 68.6 c/ha.

When we determined the relationship between the traits, it was found that there was a strong positive relationship between total chlorophyll and carotenoids ($r = 94^{***}$), a medium positive relationship with leaf surface ($r = 54^*$), a strong positive relationship with yield ($r = 95^{***}$) and an average positive relationship with the daily net productivity of photosynthesis. To determine the results, the regression coefficient was determined using the regression equation. The relationship between total chlorophyll and yield was estimated using a linear equation, that is, it was theoretically calculated that increasing total chlorophyll by a certain amount would increase productivity by how many grams.

In the regression analysis results, the blue dots on the graph are the total amount of chlorophyll, and the red dots are the estimated or theoretical increase in yield. As can be seen from the equation, $y = 0.0082x - 2.85$ - the regression coefficient on the graph is equal to 0.0082%. It is shown that the increase in the total amount of chlorophyll at 1 mg/g leads to an increase in fertility by 0.0082 g/m², up to 12%. Comparing the total amount of chlorophylls in the studied samples with net photosynthetic productivity and crop yield, the three-year content of chlorophylls changed from 3.34 mg/g to 2.03 mg/g, and a decrease in yield was observed significantly in samples with reduced chlorophyll content.

The accumulation of dry matter in bread wheat is one of the important parameters that determine photosynthetic productivity and yield. In our three-year analysis results, the overall average photosynthetic productivity of the samples was 5.34 g/m². day. In the variety "Krasnodarskaya - 99" the daily productivity of photosynthesis was 5.47 g/m².day, which is higher than that of the collection samples. In samples with net photosynthetic productivity above 6 g/m².day, there was an increase in yield up to 70 c/ha, total leaf surface up to 71 cm² (except for sample K-46), dry matter accumulation level up to 234 mg, total chlorophyll content from 2.62 to 3.34 mg

When studying the influence of samples on photosynthesis, chlorophyll and yield, it was found that yield increased in samples K-7 (6.25±0.35), K-13 (6.36±0.56), K-46 (6.39±0.62), and K-64 (6.48±0.62) having a high daily net productivity of photosynthesis. The remaining samples did not differ significantly from each other. In samples with a net photosynthetic productivity of more than 6 g/m².day, the weight of 1000 grains is 47.7 g, the number of spikelets in one ear is 17, the length of the ear is 10.6 cm, the weight of grains in the weight of one ear is 2.23 g, the number of grains in one ear is 47.1 units. caused the ear weight to be more than 3.1 g.

When we assessed whether there was statistical differentiation between samples, we found that samples K-8, K-46 and K-81 were grouped together and had significant differences compared to samples K-7, K-13, K-64 and K-80. The remaining samples did not show any significant differences from each other. It was noted that accessions with higher leaf surface area also had higher daily photosynthetic productivity and yield.

The fact that photosynthesis had a positive effect on daily net productivity and yield in high chlorophyll samples indicates a positive correlation between physiological traits and quantitative traits.

The results of the analysis show that between photosynthetic productivity and total leaf surface there is a strong positive $r = 0.82^{***}$, an average positive $r = 0.59^{**}$ with total chlorophyll, an average positive $r = 0.59^{**}$ with the rate of dry matter accumulation substances, weak positive $r = 0.26$ with total biological dry weight, average positive $r = 0.69^{**}$ with yield, with the weight of 1000 grains ($r = 0.14$), with the number of spikelets in one ear ($r = 0.33$), ear length ($r = 0.43^*$), grain weight in one ear ($r = 0.41$), number of grains ($r = 0.46^*$) and ear weight ($r = 0.44^*$) revealed the presence weak positive connection.

CONCLUSION

In the results of the study of the influence of the genotype-environment on the physiological and quantitative characteristics of the collection of bread wheat in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the following conclusions were presented:

When analyzing the influence among the genotype, it was revealed that with the hydrothermal coefficient $I_j = 1.43$ in 2017, the average yield from all nurseries was 68.4 c/ha, in 2019 with $I_j = 0.69$ the yield was 87.7 c/ha. Samples were identified according to indicators of environmental plasticity

(bi) and stability coefficient (Si^2). Samples K-64 (bi =0,5, Si^2 =1,8), K-74 (bi =0,7, Si^2 =1,9) and sample K-100 (bi =0,4, Si^2 =0,9).

Regression analysis showed that a 1 mg increase in total chlorophyll in the 50 selected samples increased productivity by 12%, in which the three-year average total chlorophyll amount was from 3.34 mg/g to 2.03 mg/g. d, and productivity in samples with low chlorophyll content is also significantly reduced;

A strong positive correlation was found between net productivity of photosynthesis and leaf area $r=0.82$, between productivity and photosynthesis $r=0.69$, between leaf area and transpiration coefficient $r=0.64$, average positive $r=0.59^{**}$ with total productivity of chlorophyll and photosynthesis between productivity $r=0.58$, positive accumulation of dry matter $r=0.51^*$, negative, with water-holding capacity $r=-0.09$.

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